

The Zi-Biao S lines are indica-type PTGMS lines derived from the cross between Tan-Zi, a purple-leaf indica rice variety, and 1356 S, an indica PTGMS line. These lines had slower critical sterility temperature than the parent lines. Under 14-h daylength and under controlled conditions, pollen sterility was more than 99.9% and seed

Table 1. Pollen sterility of Zi-Biao S lines under artificial climate chamber.

PTGMS	Stage of panicle development ^a	Daily mean temperature (°C)	Mean pollen sterility (%)
Zi-Biao S-1	III	24.07	99.99
	IV	24.07	99.99
	V	24.03	99.99
	VI	23.01	100.00
Zi-Biao S-2	III	24.00	99.99
	IV	23.01	99.99
	V	23.91	99.99
	VI	23.97	99.99

^a Treatment period was 4 d; sample size was 10 plants in each treatment.

Table 2. Main agronomic and outcrossing characters of Zi Biao S lines. Guizhou, China.

Line	Plant height (cm)	Panicles plant ⁻¹ (no.)	Spikelets panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	Grain weight (g)	Days to heading	Rice quality	Spikelets (%)	Exserted stigma (%)	Response to GA ₃	Angle of glume opening
Zi Biao S-1	59.7	7.5	113.6	23.0	85	Good	29.8	69.1	Sensitive	45°
Zi Biao S-2	55.8	7.0	129.0	23.0	94	Good	36.3	63.2	Sensitive	41°

set under bagging was zero (Table 1). Under natural photoperiod and temperatures in Guidion, Guizhou (26°35' N, elevation of 1006 m), the pollen sterility of plants which flowered from 18 Jul to 29 Aug was 100%, and the complete male sterile period was 43 d. Plants which flowered after 30 Aug reverted to fertility (pollen fertility ranged from 15 to 50%).

During the fertile period, seed setting was 21.4% in Zi-Biao S-1 and 54.1% in Zi-Biao S-2. The average temperatures in the first, second, and last 10 d were 22.0, 25.1, and 28.4 °C in Jul 1995 and 24.5, 23.5, and 25.3 °C in Aug 1995. The monthly average day-

length was 13.61 h in Jul 1995 and 13.02 h in Aug 1995.

Their agronomic characters and outcrossing traits were superior (Table 2). The presence of purple leaf at the seedling stage can be used as marker for eliminating selfed-seedlings of the PTGMS line in F₁, that result from incomplete male sterility of PTGMS line owing to consecutive lower temperatures (>4 d, <24 °C) in two-line hybrid seed production. Other rice varieties mixed inadvertently in multiplication of the PTGMS line can also be easily removed by using the purple leaf as a marker. Thus, these lines will be useful in maintaining the purity of hybrid crops. ■

High-frequency plant generation in wild species of *Oryza*

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We are developing a system for Plant regeneration from wild species of *Oryza*. In recent work, dehusked seeds were surface-sterilized with 0.1% (w/v) HgCl₂ solution for 5 min and rinsed four times in sterile distilled water. Sterilized seeds were kept for germination on MS medium devoid of growth hormones in light (1600 lux) at 25 °C. The endosperm and radicle were excised from 7-d-old seedlings, which were then inoculated on MS medium supplemented with 6.0 mg BAP L⁻¹. Multiple shoots or micropropagules developed at the base of shoots were used for callus initiation. Segments

(0.5-1.0 cm long) cut from their white tissue were inoculated on LS medium containing 2.5 mg 2,4-DL⁻¹, 3% sucrose, and pH was adjusted to 5.8. The cultures were kept in the light. Embryogenic calli from the primary cultures were subcultured on the same medium and then transferred to regeneration medium based on MS salts supplemented with 2.0 mg BAP L⁻¹ and 0.5 mg NAAL⁻¹. All media were solidified with phytigel (0.2% Sigma) and growth hormones avoided. Rooted plantlets were transferred to pots.

Callus induction was observed in all wild species. Normally, callus developed at both the nodal and internodal regions of the propagules (see figure, a). Induction frequency varied among species. An embryogenic type of calli—compact, globular, shiny, and white or pale yellow—developed in all the wild species, whereas both accessions of *O. meridionalis* produced fast-growing nonembryogenic calli. Plant regenera-

a. Callus development from nodal and internodal regions of the shoot bases of *O. nivara*. **b.** High-frequency plant regeneration in *O. nivara*. **c.** Rooting of regenerated plantlets derived from *O. nivara*. **d.** Field transfer of plantlets raised in vitro.

tion also varied among species (see table). Both accessions of *O. meridionalis* failed to regenerate into plantlets and

their calli, when subcultured, turned into roots and further proliferation of calli occurred. In all remaining wild species, plantlets developed through embryoid germination. A high frequency of plant regeneration was observed in *O. nirvana* (see figure, b) and *O. rufipogon* (Acc. 104311), whereas low frequency of plant regeneration was observed in *O. rufipogon* (Acc. 104308) and *O. longistaminata*. Embryogenic calli derived from *O. eichingeri* cultured on the same regeneration media failed to regenerate. Root initiation was observed after transferring shoots to growth hormone-free MS medium (see figure, c). Regenerated plants were grown successfully in the field (see figure, d) and seeds were harvested. This system of plant regeneration from embryogenic callus can provide a useful material for the improvement of rice by use of plant biotechnology. ■

Callus induction and plant regeneration from shoot base explant of different wild species of *Oryza*.^a Jaipur, India.

Wild species of <i>Oryza</i>	Callus induction		Plant regeneration		
	Explants planted (no.)	Explants responding (no.)	Calli planted (no.)	Regenerating calli (no.)	Mean±SE
<i>O. meridionalis</i> (Acc. 101147)	42	32	24	NR ^b	-
<i>O. meridionalis</i> (Acc. 101148)	35	35	26	NR	-
<i>O. rufipogon</i> (Acc. 104308)	36	24	24	11	15.0 ± 1.63
<i>O. rufipogon</i> (Acc. 104311)	37	25	25	16	50.60 ± 3.26
<i>O. eichingeri</i> (Acc. 105152)	47	22	21	NR	-
<i>O. nivara</i> (Acc. 101994)	33	33	30	22	26.66 ± 6.80
<i>O. longistaminata</i> (Acc. 101211)	45	31	30	11	2.60 ± 0.24

^aCallusing medium LS + 2.5 mg 2,4-DL⁻¹; regeneration medium MS + 2.0 mg BAP L⁻¹ + 0.5 mg NAA L⁻¹. ONR = no response; SE = standard error; - = no value.

Anther culture of indica/Basmati rice heterotic F₁ and F₂ hybrids and selection of desirable double haploid lines

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Anther culture has been useful for the introgression of desirable traits into breeding populations of rice. We have been working on the transfer of dwarfness, defense against brown plant-hopper attack, and resistance to bacterial blight, from indica rice varieties to Basmati rice. This study included 12 indica rice varieties with one or more of the above mentioned desirable traits, six Basmati rice cultivars/breeding lines, and 31 heterotic F₁/F₂ hybrids obtained from different indica / Basmati crosses. Basmati rice parents included Basmati 370, Basmati 385, Pusa Basmati 1 (semidwarf), and advanced breeding lines (HBC5, HBC19, and

HBC143) derived from Taraori Basmati. Panicles were collected from nethouse plants when the distance between flag leaf and penultimate leaf was 4-5 cm. Anthers were cultured in 9 cm petri dishes containing 30 ml N6 and MO19 media supplemented with either 2.0 mg NAAL⁻¹, 1.0 mg kinetin L⁻¹, and 0.5 mg 2,4-DL⁻¹, or 1.0 mg kinetin L⁻¹ and 2.0 mg 2,4-DL⁻¹. MO19 is a modified MS medium which contains 3,134 mg KNO₃L⁻¹, 320 mg (NH₄)₂SO₄L⁻¹, 540 mg KH₂PO₄L⁻¹ and lacks NH₄NO₃. The media contained 40 g sucrose L⁻¹. Cultured anthers were subjected to a cold treatment at 10°C for 10 d and incubated under dark at 24±1°C. Data were recorded on percentage of anthers forming calli after 60 d. Microcalli at 2-4 mm diam were transferred to a modified MS medium containing 0.5 mg NAA L⁻¹ and 1.0 mg each of BAP and kinetin L⁻¹, kept under fluorescent light of 50 µE m⁻²s⁻¹. Data were recorded on calli regenerating green and /or albino shoots after 30 d. Shoots were rooted and hardened in one-half strength MS medium supplemented with 0.25 mg NAAL⁻¹ and 2.5 mg multieffect tri-

azole L⁻¹ (MET, CNRRI, Hangzhou, China). All the media were semi-solidified using 0.25% (w/v) phytagel (SIGMA, USA). Regenerated plants were transferred and grown to maturity in the nethouse.

Representative data are shown in the table. An advanced indica rice breeding line IET12012 showed a high frequency of androgenic calli formation (5.5%) as well as green plant regeneration (10 plants per 1000 anthers). In general, F₂ hybrids responded better to anther culture than F₁ hybrids. The F₂ hybrids involving IET21012 as the female parent were responsive to anther culture. Basmati rice genotypes were less responsive. Anthers from the F₁ indica/Basmati hybrid populations involving HBC19 produced a greater number of embryogenic calli and green plants than those from Basmati 370. A sufficient number of green plants could be obtained from some F₁/F₂ heterotic hybrids and transferred to the greenhouse.

The success of transplantation of regenerated green plants to soil conditions during late February to end of